

D5.4

ENVRI Service Catalogue

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Deliverable abstract

The Deliverable "D5.4 ENVRI Service Catalogue" presents the development, implementation, and operation of a comprehensive service catalogue within the context of the ENVRI-FAIR project. The deliverable outlines the creation of a FAIR compliant and EOSC-ready catalogue, primarily focusing on services providing access to data. The innovative design and implementation of the catalogue embrace the adoption of rich metadata standards for ingestion and storage, namely EPOS-DCAT-AP metadata profile and the CERIF model, facilitating the description of diverse services across different research infrastructures (RIs). The validation processes, including service validation at the subdomain level, FAIRness evaluation, and an implementation phase, ensure the robustness, accuracy, and FAIR compliance of the catalogue, promoting its interoperability with the EOSC catalogue.

The deliverable further details the operation of the catalogue, which involves a harmonised effort among service providers, backend developers, and front-end developers. It underscores the ongoing endeavour to ingest more metadata records, provide support for metadata curation, and work towards semantic interoperability. Future work, as outlined in the deliverable, involves enhancing the catalogue's operation by improving metadata quality, enhancing semantic interoperability, and adapting to the diversity of service types from different RIs.

The ENVRI Service Catalogue represents a pivotal step towards advancing FAIR practices in environmental research. Its development, implementation, and operation symbolise an ongoing commitment to continuous improvement, adaptation, and learning, with the ultimate goal of propelling environmental research towards new horizons of discovery and innovation. By aligning with the EOSC catalogue requirements, it envisions a broader, more integrated network of scientific resources, thus empowering global researchers. The ENVRI Service Catalogue, as the embodiment of the ENVRI-FAIR project's vision, promises to facilitate open, FAIR, and efficient access to services and data in the environmental research domain.

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Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

GLOSSARY

A relevant project glossary is included in Appendix A. The latest version of the master list of the glossary is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471374>.

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions, and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent, and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services.

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D5.4 - ENVRI Service Catalogue

1 Introduction

This document represents Deliverable 5.4, the ENVRI Service Catalogue, of the ENVRI-FAIR project. It documents the development and operation of the ENVRI Service Catalogue, highlighting its role as a central hub for environmental research services. The catalogue, developed by Task Force 1 (TF1), draws together a diverse array of services offered by RIs across four scientific subdomains, namely Solid Earth, Atmosphere, Marine and Biodiversity-Ecosystem. It provides a streamlined and user-friendly platform that enables researchers to efficiently discover and access services that cater to their specific research needs.

In the following sections of this deliverable, we outline the journey of the catalogue's development, from background work through design and implementation, to the validation and operation of the catalogue. We also look ahead to future work planned to further enhance the utility and effectiveness of this tool.

Section 2, Background Work, outlines the initial steps and considerations in the development of the catalogue. This process involved a careful review of existing service catalogues and an understanding of the specific requirements of the ENVRI community. From this research, the project team leveraged on the existing EPOS-DCAT Application Profile as a template for service description, creating a unified metadata structure for the catalogue, which is in turn based on the CERIF standard.

Section 3, Design and Implementation of the Service Catalogue, details the technical aspects of the catalogue's creation. Here we elaborate on the technological infrastructure, the use of APIs, the construction of the user interface, and the process of metadata ingestion. This section illustrates the concerted efforts of service providers, backend developers, and front-end developers in bringing the ENVRI Catalogue to life.

Section 4, Validation of the Catalogue of Services, examines the steps taken to ensure the functionality and effectiveness of the catalogue. This section delves into the validation process at the subdomain level, the FAIRness evaluation of the provided services, and the implementation of service validation. It demonstrates the checks established to ensure the catalogue's quality and reliability.

Section 5, Operation of the Catalogue of Services, looks at the real-world operation of the catalogue. This section explores how the catalogue serves as a dynamic hub for environmental research services, the ongoing efforts to improve and expand the catalogue, and the challenges encountered in ensuring semantic interoperability and managing the diversity of service types.

Section 6, Future Work, outlines the task force's plans for the continued development and enhancement of the catalogue. It emphasises the ongoing commitment to improving the catalogue's operation, including efforts to enhance semantic interoperability, improve metadata records' quality, and adapt to the diverse service types from different RIs.

Finally, in Section 7, Conclusion, we reflect on the catalogue's significance within the ENVRI-FAIR project and its broader implications for the scientific community. We highlight the catalogue as a cornerstone in the project's mission to foster a unified, accessible, and FAIR ecosystem for environmental research.

By describing the concerted efforts in the creation of the ENVRI Service Catalogue, the deliverables demonstrate the project's commitment to fostering a more accessible, interoperable, and reusable landscape for environmental research, in line with the vision of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

2 Background work

The ENVRI-FAIR Task Force 1 (TF1) was responsible, since the beginning of the project, for the establishment of a metadata catalogue schema mapping existing data and data product access services. The final goal is to outline and facilitate access to the assets available from the ENVRI Research Infrastructures (RIs). The ENVRI-FAIR landscape hosts a diverse collection of research infrastructures, each with distinct characteristics in terms of dataset presentation and accessibility, format and semantics, access methods, resources of interest, and served audiences. This heterogeneity presents a significant challenge when attempting to establish interoperability. The common goal across these diverse subdomain infrastructures is to achieve interoperability through the application of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles, and the harmonisation of semantic and technical

aspects, as described in the TF1 white paper¹, which also summarise much of the work done in the first two years after the establishment of the Task Force.

To achieve this interoperability, TF1 adopted a multi-pronged approach. They recognised the necessity of a rich metadata schema that could accommodate the existing complexity of the landscape. This schema represents diverse information related to resources, such as services, datasets, codes, and publications, as well as details about persons, organisations, facilities, equipment, and authorisation. It needs to do this in a manner that is machine-readable and machine understandable.

TF1 also recognised that simply combining metadata from the RIs would not suffice. The metadata needed to be harmonised. This led to the adoption of a canonical superset-rich metadata catalogue based on the CERIF model². This catalogue represents descriptions of services from RIs implementing rich metadata, ensuring machine readability and understandability, while maintaining formal syntax and declared semantics.

The catalogue is populated with existing resources and assets, represented by metadata records describing datasets and services, but it can be potentially extended to store workflows/tools, e-services, and other assets such as equipment. Thus, the catalogue provides a “translated” heterogeneous individual information from the RIs into a homogeneous format for facilitating the end users in accessing the RI’s data, data products and services.

A key aspect of TF1’s work is the establishment of interoperability with the EOSC catalogue. This process was envisaged, at the beginning, as a two-way engagement: from the ENVRI-FAIR catalogue to the EOSC catalogue (ENVRI-to-EOSC), and vice versa (EOSC-to-ENVRI). This interoperability would have ensured that the ENVRI-FAIR catalogue acts as the entry point for details about ENV RIs, which can then interoperate with the EOSC catalogue. Additionally, users searching the EOSC catalogue could invoke services from ENV RIs, and the EOSC catalogue could be used by ENVRI-FAIR to make use of EOSC resources. During the journey leading to the construction of the ENVRI Catalogue of Services the above two-fold approach was slightly revised as shown in the next sections.

The task force also acknowledges the importance of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), which includes aspects of ethics, gender balance, governance, open access, public engagement, science and education. This informs the processes around the metadata catalogue, which then dictates the information required in the catalogue to fulfil these processes.

The work of TF1 also involved a landscaping exercise³, which reported on the status of all RIs within the TF1, focusing on the methodologies used to access their resources. This exercise provided insights into the heterogeneity of the RIs, which are captured in the common canonical superset-rich metadata description.

The task force strived to create a convergence on the definition of "services" and the metadata required for the catalogue. They’ve acknowledged the limitations of the metadata schema proposed in the context of EOSC Hub and considered well-tested options like the metadata catalogue used by the EPOS RI⁴.

3 Design and implementation of the Service Catalogue

The creation of the ENVRI Service Catalogue was a significant undertaking, initiated following the Lund meeting 30.10.2019⁵. The task of designing and implementing this catalogue was allocated to the ENVRI Catalogue of Services task force1 (TF1), whose pivotal progress was marked during the ENVRI Week in Dresden, Germany, in February 2020 and subsequently in Leipzig in 2023 (as documented in D5.2, Adamaki et al. 2020).

The primary challenge addressed by TF1 was the heterogeneity of metadata stemming from various Research Infrastructures (RIs) within ENVRI-FAIR. The group analysed the outcomes of previous

¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/6397051#.ZF5AYy9Bxqs> (accessed on 15.5.2023)

² <https://eurocris.org/services/main-features-cerif> (accessed on 15.5.2023)

³ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1oAwGhNZAwJSd-OIKxvqfOC1pyVROKiZyNQUR7nXd-L0/edit#gid=0> (accessed on 15.5.2023)

⁴ <https://www.epos-eu.org/> (accessed on 15.5.2023)

⁵ ENVRI-FAIR Milestone 15 <https://www.google.com/url?q=https://iagos-comm.fz-juelich.de/dmsf/files/3905/view&sa=D&source=docs&ust=1684224879381318&usg=AOvVaw05aw-aru9svp2e3-K4TWFk> (accessed on 15.5.2023)

projects, notably ENVRI⁶ and ENVRIplus⁷, and considered the "Canonical Catalogue" approach, which entailed setting up two catalogues with different metadata standards - CKAN metadata as utilised in EUDAT and CERIF metadata as employed in EPOS. Despite the production of prototypes in ENVRIplus, no definitive conclusion was reached.

TF1's objectives were clear: create a catalogue of services within ENVRI-FAIR to support FAIRness (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability), ensure that the Catalogue is EOSC-ready (European Open Science Cloud), and define services providing access to data rather than mapping all metadata. This perspective was premised on the understanding that Research Infrastructures provide access to data, and metadata is used to search, discover, and contextualise the digital assets - and if necessary to protect the digital assets from unauthorised access.

TF1 Objectives are coherent with the general requirements outlined in D5.1 "requirement analysis, technology review and gap analysis of environmental RIs" (also available on the project intranet⁸). These requirements, a subset of which is summarised in Table I, detail what FAIR gaps should be filled to achieve an increased FAIRness of the subdomain RIs services but are of course also valid for the ENVRI catalogue of services. It is important to note that not a few requirements still need to be satisfied by the catalogue of services (e.g., Functionalities for user interaction and feedback), which paves the way for additional future work.

Table I: a subset of the requirements emerging from D5.1

Requirement	Description
Comprehensive scope and classification of services	The catalogue should encompass a broad range of services and classify them in an organised manner.
Facilitate the discovery of services and ensure accessibility	The catalogue should have a user-friendly interface for users to easily find and access services.
Support for interlinking between datasets, publications, and other outputs or services	Users should be able to establish connections between related datasets, publications, and other services.
Inclusion of data quality information	The catalogue should include information on the quality and reliability of the data provided by the services.
Functionalities for user interaction and feedback	The catalogue should enable users to interact with the services, provide feedback, and contribute to the content.
Compliance with data and metadata standards, vocabularies, and protocols	The catalogue should adhere to relevant standards for data and metadata and utilise consistent vocabularies and protocols.
Support for data citation and inclusion of citation metrics	The catalogue should facilitate data citation and provide information on how often datasets have been cited.
Information on data policies, data management plans, and licensing terms	The catalogue should provide clear information on policies for data usage, data management plans, and licensing terms.
Adherence to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)	The catalogue should ensure that data is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable according to FAIR principles.

⁶ The central goal of the ENVRI project was the implementation of harmonised solutions and drawing up guidelines for the common needs of the environmental ESFRI projects, with a special focus on issues as architectures, metadata frameworks, data discovery in scattered repositories, visualisation and data curation.

ENVRI was funded through the EU 7th Framework Programme.

⁷ ENVRIplus is a Horizon 2020 project bringing together Environmental and Earth System Research Infrastructures, projects and networks together with technical specialist partners to create a more coherent, interdisciplinary and interoperable cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures across Europe.

⁸ <https://iagos-comm.fz-juelich.de/dmsf/files/4111/view>

Requirement	Description
Provision of machine-readable metadata in a formal language and use of semantic vocabularies for data classification	The catalogue should provide metadata in a machine-readable format and use semantic vocabularies to classify data effectively.

To this end, a generic architectural approach was presented, though it was still a topic of discussion at the time. This architecture model was composed of two main modalities for accessing services: a) through Web-APIs, which can be accessed by machines and easily upgraded to be FAIR as they are potentially machine-readable and machine-understandable, and b) through Portals, which are primarily accessible by humans but still provide access to datasets, as shown in Fig.1.

Figure 1: ENVRI-FAIR catalogue of services basic architecture. The underlying idea is that any Research Infrastructure provides access, ultimately, to data, and that metadata is used to search, discover and contextualise the data. Then, the data searched through metadata is made available through “services”. Although the definition of services is still under discussion in TF1, two main modalities for accessing the services were identified: a) through Web-APIs, for instance restful web-services, that can be accessed by machines and that are easily upgradable to be FAIR as they are potentially machine-readable and machine-understandable, and b) through Portals, mostly accessible by humans, but yet an asset providing access to the datasets. The orange layer represents the ENVRI Fair Catalogue of services, while the blue box represents components of the underlying RIs.

Progress on the design of the Service Catalogue was marked by several key achievements. First, RIs were actively involved through use cases. TF1 prepared a spreadsheet for the collection of potential "resources" such as services, portals, datasets, or other assets. This exercise aimed to map all available services from RIs technically, guiding them step-by-step towards a definitive technical definition of their assets to be included in the catalogue (this was the already mentioned landscaping exercise).

Second, the objectives and catalogue schema were defined. This was achieved through intense discussions around a collaboratively written document that described the status, objectives, progress, and future work of TF1. The document led to the identification of CERIF as a potential candidate for the ENVRI-FAIR catalogue of services. The discussions also acknowledged issues such as the heterogeneity of metadata and interoperability with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

The third achievement was leveraging existing solutions to identify the most suitable approach, including both metadata standard and existing technologies to underpin it. By maintaining a pragmatic approach, TF1 agreed on a consensus to leverage existing solutions leading quickly towards a proof-of-concept implementation, thus ensuring that the efforts dedicated to the development of the catalogue were well-grounded and capitalised.

The proposed solution was therefore derived from the EPOS Research Infrastructure architecture. RIs within ENVRI-FAIR can describe services or portals by means of metadata that can ultimately be

ingested into the EPOS metadata catalogue, (based on CERIF) and ingests metadata in an extension of the DCAT-AP application profile, namely the EPOS-DCAT-AP⁹ metadata profile.

Figure 2: EPOS Integrated Core Services - Central HUB basic architecture. The picture represents the basic architecture of the EPOS RIs. The main component, with respect to the main topic of the current document, is the CERIF metadata catalogue included in the ICS purple layer. The metadata schema is rich enough to store details about the services provided by the underlying system, TCS (thematic Core Services) in the EPOS jargon, which corresponds to the RIs in ENVRI-FAIR.

The architecture is described in detail elsewhere¹⁰, and it is out of the scope of this document to go into the details of this description. Leveraging on this approach, the main idea is that RIs within ENVRI-FAIR can describe services or portal (represented by the “TCS” yellow boxes in Figure 2) by means of metadata that can ultimately be ingested into the ICS-C metadata catalogue and ingests metadata in a DCAT-AP application profile to which other metadata formats may readily be converted (to the already mentioned EPOS-DCAT-AP).

This solution found a good consensus within TF1 meetings and was firstly implemented as proof-of-concept in order to be further validated and investigated, then confirmed for the final implementation of the catalogue.

In parallel, successive iterations of the EOSC metadata ‘schema’ (known as “profiles”) were mapped to CERIF in preparation for onboarding the services within the ENVRI catalogue to EOSC. Furthermore, discussions were initiated with OpenAIRE as a possible alternative mechanism for onboarding to EOSC. These discussions continue.

The design and implementation of the Service Catalogue were therefore guided by a consensus-based approach, focusing on a pragmatic approach, and leveraging existing solutions. The approach ensured the creation of a catalogue that supports the FAIR principles, is EOSC-ready, and primarily describes services providing access to data. Moving forward, the next steps involve mapping RI metadata formats to the canonical metadata model and mapping the canonical metadata model to the services catalogue.

The ENVRI Catalogue of Services is currently implemented based on the open-source EPOS Data Portal system¹¹. The EPOS Catalogue, which is also open source under the GPL3 license, utilises a modular architecture (Microservices Approach) and open technologies (Docker Containers over Kubernetes Cluster), as explained in the software documentation¹². This approach ensures interoperability and enables seamless integration of research infrastructure services within the ENVRI Cluster. By leveraging open-source software and adopting an open license, the ENVRI Catalogue promotes collaboration, transparency, and adherence to open standards in the Environmental research community.

⁹ <https://github.com/epos-eu/EPOS-DCAT-AP> (accessed on 15.5.2023)

¹⁰ All documentation available here: <https://github.com/epos-eu/documentation>

¹¹ <https://epos-eu.github.io/epos-open-source/>

¹² <https://epos-eu.github.io/epos-open-source/doc.html>

4 Validation of the Catalogue of Services

The Validation of the Services in the ENVRI Service Catalogue followed specific guidelines designed to ensure the robustness, accuracy, and FAIRness (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) of the listed services. Such guidelines have been issued following the test guideline in the D7.7 (Thijssse et al. 2022).

These guidelines were not created in isolation but were connected to the work conducted across various subdomains of ENVRI-FAIR, including the design and implementation of the Service Catalogue, and its operation. The validation process primarily involved two three interconnected activities: service validation at the subdomain level, FAIRness evaluation of the provided services and implementation of the catalogue and its validation.

4.1 Service validation at the subdomain level

The service validation at the subdomain level was focused on defining test plans for ENVRI services and use cases, while the latter on assessing the FAIRness of the provided services, contributing to a wider evolution towards FAIR activities within the subdomains. The FAIRness evaluation is based on a method that combines existing practices and methods from the communities and was used fully in WP10 (see for instance D10.3) and partially by other subdomains, as already described in D5.5 and adopted in other domains¹³ (Bailo, D. *et al.* (2020)).

The service validation process was synchronised with the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) common to all Research Infrastructures (RIs), and more generally to all those producing software for data stewardship services.

This validation process is divided into three steps. The first step involves analysing FAIR principles and providing an evaluation with respect to the existing landscape. The second step is devoted to the evaluation and gap analysis to understand the priority by which FAIR principles at each stage need to be addressed. The third step, based on the gap analysis, involves selecting technical activities to undertake and then actual implementation.

The ENVRI-FAIR project has already implemented these steps as part of the subdomain work, described in the deliverables of the specific subdomains (D8.3, D9.2, D10.2, D10.3, D11.1, D11.2, all referenced in the “references” section).

4.2 FAIRness evaluation of the provided services

The FAIRness assessment of the provided services provided an up-to-date gap analysis of the most common gaps the ENVRI needed to bridge with respect to the FAIR principles¹⁴, as outlined in the landscaping exercise¹⁵. Following this assessment, an implementation plan was prepared, based on the common development targets defined in the gap analysis. The ENVRI worked on their FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs)¹⁶, which capture the FAIR implementation choices made by the RIs. In terms of the ENVRI-FAIR service catalogue, several criteria have been defined for integration. First, all services included in the catalogue need to be described by means of rich metadata, which is fundamental for sharing assets with external initiatives. Second, a clear definition of the types of assets to be included in the catalogue should be provided. This ensures that any potential consumers of the catalogue will understand whether the assets consumed are machine-actionable or human-readable. Lastly, it is important to ensure that the assets provided and described in the catalogue are tested, validated, and compliant with the FAIR principles.

These criteria ensure that the assets included in the catalogue were validated with an adequate level of robustness and richness in terms of metadata description, so that these can be easily interoperated with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) catalogue.

¹⁴ FAIRness assessment is dealt with in D5.1 - first FAIR assessment and gap analysis, D5.2 - common development targets for implementation plan based on gap analysis

¹⁵ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1oAwGhNZAwJSd-OIKxvqfOC1pyVROKiZyNQUr7nXd-L0/edit#gid=0> (accessed on 15.5.2023)

¹⁶ See Deliverable D5.6

4.3 Implementation of the catalogue and its validation

As the catalogue brings together services produced at subdomain RI level, where the Service validation at the subdomain level already occurred, the service validation of the services in the catalogue focused on the suitability of the services for the end users and did not get into the details of the technical gaps, that are tackled in the subdomains to improve RI specific services. Therefore, the already mentioned three key criteria were used. Firstly, all services included in the catalogue need to be described by means of rich metadata, particularly with respect to the metadata elements necessary for machine actionability (such as web-service query parameters). This enhances the discoverability and interoperability of the services.

Secondly, a clear metadata definition of the types of assets to be included in the catalogue was developed. This ensures that potential consumers of the catalogue can understand whether the assets consumed are machine-actionable or human-readable. It contributes to the usability of the catalogue and promotes a seamless user experience.

The third criterion seeks to ensure that the assets provided and described in the catalogue are compliant with the FAIR principles as much as possible. In particular, this includes the assignment of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) and the completeness of the Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) system. These aspects contribute significantly to the findability and accessibility of the services.

Most of these criteria were tackled by the FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIP) activity, described in D5.6 and in some scientific publications (Magagna, B. et al. (2020).), which focused on the key FAIR aspects of each of the services. These profiles were then combined into a FAIR convergence matrix which represents the FAIRness level of the ENVRI and their progress towards becoming more FAIR as a community.

An effective means of validation has been the ingestion process of the service within the catalogue: indeed, once an asset is clearly defined and described with rich metadata that adheres to a commonly accepted schema, the metadata can be ingested into the ENVRI catalogue. The Catalogue of services then offers a first testbed for the validation of the service in terms of richness of metadata. At a higher level of validation and testing, the asset should also comply with the minimum requirements defined by the EOSC portal to be onboarded to the EOSC catalogue, but this goes beyond the goals of the current deliverable.

5 Operation of the Catalogue of Services

The primary function of the ENVRI Catalogue of Services is to act as a hub, offering access to different Research Infrastructure (RI) services. The catalogue was created in three stages. First, the metadata descriptions were curated by individual RI service providers following an EPOS-DCAT-AP template. The mapping between EPOS-DCAT-AP metadata, ENVRI Catalogue APIs, ENVRI Catalogue GUI was fully described in a dedicated documentation file¹⁷. These metadata descriptions were then uploaded as turtle files onto an EPOS GitLab account^{18,19}. The decision to work via the upload of metadata descriptions, rather than harvesting the metadata RDF/TTL directly from the sources, was driven by the recognition that for many data providers (RIs), publishing a “good” metadata description to be harvested can be a challenge. By manually drafting the metadata descriptions, metadata curators can ensure a higher quality of metadata. This approach allows curators to carefully craft and review each metadata record, ensuring that all the necessary information is accurately represented. It provides an opportunity to address any inconsistencies or gaps in the metadata and ensure that the descriptions are comprehensive and informative. While this process may require more effort and time initially, it ensures a controlled and quality-driven approach to metadata creation. As the ENVRI Catalogue of Services evolves, the long-term vision should still encourage service providers to publish metadata alongside their services in a standardised format. This would enable seamless integration and improved discoverability, while ensuring that high-quality metadata remains a priority for the ENVRI community within the EOSC ecosystem.

In the second stage, backend work involved writing APIs that could read the turtle files and return various information in a format suitable for the Catalogue's front-end developers. The final stage involved the actual construction (jointly with the developers of ENVRI-Hub) of the user interface (UI) of the

¹⁷ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1P8NL3FqEcipm4kTOAw8tt3xHhCYfc1WT/view?usp=share_link (accessed on 15.5.2023)

¹⁸ <https://epos-ci.brgm.fr/ics-tcs/epos-dcat-ap/envri> (accessed on 15.5.2023)

¹⁹ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1CZZTYq4t3OkBk0H2rO-skKCwae6SKwri/view?usp=share_link (accessed on 15.5.2023)

Catalogue, the website, with contents constructed from the data obtained from the APIs. The operation of the Catalogue thus required a harmonised effort among service providers, backend developers, and front-end developers. TF1 provided critical mapping between the metadata in the turtle files, those accessed via the APIs, and those appearing on the Catalogue's website. This process ensured the service providers' understanding of how their metadata appeared in the Catalogue.

Further, TF1 organised several online training and editing sessions to assist service providers in creating technically correct turtle files with the right and complete EPOS-DCAT metadata²⁰. Part of these training sessions involved adopting a limited set of controlled vocabularies to describe the science domains and the specific services. This harmonisation of terms allowed for a better user experience and future development of semantic translations in the Catalogue.

The operational website of the ENVRI Catalogue is available at <https://envri-hub.envri.eu/cservicesmain> and consists of several features.

These include a menu giving access to the Catalogue landing page, to a SPARQL search interface, and a service "alive" check. A search interface allows categorised search based on the science domain, service type, and service keywords. Search results are listed by RI, with each service's information, including spatial coverage and metadata, accessible by clicking on any search result.

The operation of the Catalogue also includes the ingestion of further metadata records from the subdomains, necessitating support for communities appointed as metadata editors for updating and integrating metadata records. Simultaneously, work is ongoing to improve the quality of metadata records and to make vocabularies consistent and interoperable. This will provide a better user experience, aligned with the EOSC catalogue requirements, and enabling a simple discovery of available services. This is a continuous endeavour that is part of the activities planned for the sustainability of the catalogue. In terms of challenges, the heterogeneity of service types and scientific domains required extensive semantic work to ensure an improved user experience and semantic interoperability. TF1 successfully added three classes of keywords to each service in the Catalogue, allowing for filtering at different levels of granularity^{21,22}. However, accommodating the diversity of service types provided by RIs within one metadata profile required compromises on multiple fronts, presenting a challenge for future flexibility.

²⁰ See for instance the “ENVRI-FAIR Task Force 1 Service Catalogue tutorial” available at <https://trainingcatalogue.envri.eu/course/46> (accessed on 15.5.2023)

²¹ <https://hubtest.envri-fair.eu/dbcontent/keyword/> (accessed on 15.5.2023)

²² Keywords and other semantic element are also expressed in a turtle file (which can be downloaded from <https://vocabulary.envri-fair.eu/>), and by leveraging the Django system the terms therein were made online-resolvable by referring to them as e.g. <https://vocabulary.envri-fair.eu/hubservicetypes/CatalogueService> for the keyword “CatalogueService”. (both links accessed on 15.5.2023)

ENVRI Catalogue of Services

The ENVRI Catalogue of Services is populated by the Research Infrastructures in ENVRI-FAIR. It contains descriptions of the RI services that provide data, metadata, semantic assets, taxonomic information, and more. The focus here is on services that provide machine-accessible endpoints, and information about how to query these service endpoints is provided here.

Available Services

Filter resources: +
 Hint: Find keywords as you type...

Select a service type

Select a science domain

Select keywords

Filter Resources

Search Results:

- All 60
- ACTRIS Data Centre 5
- CREA-Consiglio per la Ricerca in Agricoltura e l'analisi dell'Economia Agraria 1
- EPOS EPOS 11**

LOS Displacement Time Series
 Temporal evolution of the surface displacement projected along the satellite Line of Sight (LOS)
 Status: ✓
[Details](#)

Unwrapped Interferograms
 Map of the flattened phase difference (full evolution) computed between two SAR images acquired over the same scene with the same geometry
 Status: ✓
[Details](#)

DEM in radar geometry
 Digital Elevation Model provided in radar coordinates
 Status: ✓
[Details](#)

Service Details

EPOS
 EUROPEAN PLATE OBSERVING SYSTEM

LOS Displacement Time Series

Temporal evolution of the surface displacement projected along the satellite Line of Sight (LOS)

Service Description Temporal evolution of the surface displacement projected along the satellite Line of Sight (LOS).

Service Documentation <https://docs.terradue.com/elli/core/da/catalog/search.html>

Service Provider EPOS

Data Provider EPOS

Temporal Coverage 1978-01-01:00Z

Resource Type WEB_SERVICE

Endpoint [https://catalog.terradue.com/gee-epos/search?format=json&epos:LOS_DISPLACEMENT_TIMESERIES\[&start_stop_geom_track_uid_od_psn_count\]&bbox={minLongitude,minLatitude,maxLongitude,maxLatitude}](https://catalog.terradue.com/gee-epos/search?format=json&epos:LOS_DISPLACEMENT_TIMESERIES[&start_stop_geom_track_uid_od_psn_count]&bbox={minLongitude,minLatitude,maxLongitude,maxLatitude})

Frequency update <http://purl.org/ctd/freq/continuous>

License <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

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Figure 3: A screenshot of the ENVRI Catalogue of Services. The left-hand side of the screen displays a comprehensive list of the various Research Infrastructures (RIs) included in the catalogue. Users can utilise the dynamic filters located above the list to narrow down their search based on specific keywords, service types, or scientific domains. This streamlined interface allows for efficient and user-friendly exploration of the extensive catalogue, promoting easier access to a diverse array of services and datasets across multiple environmental research fields. The central panel shows the selected services with the associated rich metadata, to be used for accessing the services and using it in a programmatic way through the described service APIs, when available.

The operation of the ENVRI Catalogue of Services continues to be a work in progress. The next steps include further ingestion of metadata records from the subdomains, support to communities for metadata record curation, work on making vocabularies consistent or interoperable, and onboarding to EOSC. These tasks require close collaboration with the ENVRI development team, the subdomain experts, and other ENVRI task forces.

Another very relevant result in the operation of the ENVRI Catalogue of Service is its onboarding on the EOSC marketplace platform, which will be discussed more in depth in “D5.3: Demonstrator of Service Integration In EOSC”.

Future work. The operation of the Catalogue of Services is a crucial component of the ENVRI-FAIR project. While significant strides have been made, the task force continues to work on improving the catalogue's operation. The focus remains on enhancing semantic interoperability, quality of metadata records, and adapting to the diversity of service types from different RIs. The ultimate goal is to ensure that the ENVRI Catalogue of Services becomes an effective and efficient tool for the environmental research community, providing seamless access to a broad range of services and datasets.

As part of this endeavour, the task force is constantly learning and adapting to the challenges presented by the diversity and complexity of the services offered by the RIs. This includes developing a deep

understanding of the specific requirements and constraints of different service types, and innovating ways to accommodate these within a unified metadata profile.

The operation of the Catalogue will also involve a significant amount of work in training service providers to use the new metadata standards and systems. This involves not only technical training in how to create and upload metadata records, but also conceptual work in understanding the importance of controlled vocabularies and semantic interoperability. The metadata creation and upgrade process need a critical view and constant discussion how this can be improved to a system that is not central but decentral, while making use of agreed standards for describing the services (DCAT-AP, schema.org profiles, vocabs support).

Mechanisms for onboarding to EOSC are being adopted, utilising the “profiles” schema for onboarding the portal/catalogue service and further investigating utilising the OpenAIRE route for detailed metadata records in the ENVRI catalogue.

In conclusion, the operation of the ENVRI Catalogue of Services is a dynamic and evolving process, constantly adapting, and improving to better serve the needs of the environmental research community. The work of Task Force 1 in this regard has been critical, and will continue to be so, as the Catalogue moves forward in its development and operation. The task force's ongoing commitment to enhancing the operation of the Catalogue, in close collaboration with all relevant stakeholders, will ensure that it continues to be a valuable resource for the ENVRI-FAIR project and the broader scientific community.

6 Conclusion

The development, implementation, and operation of the ENVRI Service Catalogue is a critical undertaking in the advancement of the environmental research community. This deliverable presents the collective efforts of Task Force 1 and the broader ENVRI-FAIR team in shaping a robust, comprehensive, and FAIR service catalogue.

The ENVRI Catalogue of Services stems from a broad and detailed background work (Section 2), where it leveraged the existing EPOS architecture, a decision rooted in pragmatic and consensus-based considerations. The aim was to create a catalogue that is FAIR compliant and EOSC-ready, focusing on describing services that provide access to data. This approach illustrates the commitment of the ENVRI-FAIR project to operate within established frameworks, while also contributing to their expansion and development.

The design and implementation of the Service Catalogue (Section 3) brought about an innovative solution. The catalogue embraces the EPOS-DCAT-AP metadata profile, which is both comprehensive and adaptable, allowing for the description of diverse services across different research infrastructures (RIs). The proof-of-concept phase confirmed its suitability and led to its final implementation.

The validation of the Catalogue of Services (Section 4) was conducted through rigorous processes. The validation mechanisms, including service validation at the subdomain level, FAIRness evaluation, and an implementation phase, ensured that the catalogue is robust, accurate, and adheres to the FAIR principles. The inclusion of services in the catalogue is underpinned by rich metadata descriptions, clear asset definitions, and FAIR compliance, promoting its interoperability with the EOSC catalogue.

The operation of the Catalogue (Section 5) has involved a harmonised effort among service providers, backend developers, and front-end developers. The catalogue, available at <https://envri-hub.envri.eu/cservicesmain>, not only stands as a hub for access to different RI services but also provides a user-friendly interface for efficient search and access to the services. The process of ingesting more metadata records, providing support for metadata curation, and working towards semantic interoperability is an ongoing endeavour.

In terms of future work (Section 6), the task force is committed to enhancing the catalogue's operation by improving the quality of metadata records, working on semantic interoperability, and adapting to the diversity of service types provided by different RIs. The ultimate goal is to ensure that the ENVRI Catalogue of Services becomes an effective and efficient tool for the environmental research community, offering seamless access to a broad range of services and datasets.

In closing, the ENVRI Service Catalogue is a proof of the potential of collaborative and concerted effort in advancing FAIR practices in environmental research. Its development and operation are characterised by continuous improvement, adaptation, and learning. While the catalogue is a significant achievement, the journey does not end here. The task force will continue to enhance the operation of the catalogue, in close collaboration with all relevant stakeholders, fostering its value to the ENVRI-FAIR project and the broader scientific community.

The ENVRI Service Catalogue stands as an embodiment of the ENVRI-FAIR project's vision - to facilitate open, FAIR, and efficient access to services and data in the environmental research domain. By harnessing the power of collaborative effort, shared knowledge, and innovation, we are poised to push

the boundaries of what is possible in environmental research, and in doing so, contribute to addressing some of the most pressing challenges of our time.

The pathway towards semantic interoperability, as reflected in the work on the catalogue, highlights the project's commitment to creating a unified and harmonised language for environmental research. This endeavour, while challenging due to the diversity of service types and scientific domains, underscores the importance of building bridges across different areas of expertise. By facilitating a common language for diverse research fields, the catalogue paves the way for unprecedented levels of collaboration and synergy. By adopting service publication standards, not only an ENVRI catalogue but also other national or thematic services can make use of the service metadata.

Lastly, the aspiration to align the ENVRI Service Catalogue with the EOSC catalogue requirements shows the project's broader vision. This connection will facilitate a more extensive and integrated network of scientific resources, thereby empowering researchers across the globe.

In conclusion, the ENVRI Service Catalogue is not only an accomplishment in itself, but it is also a catalyst for further achievements. It symbolises a bold step towards a future where environmental research is more accessible, interoperable, and reusable, all while fostering a sense of shared purpose and collective ambition. As we continue to navigate the complexities and challenges of our time, the ENVRI Service Catalogue will stand as a crucial tool, enabling us to make the most of our collective knowledge and resources and foster a multidisciplinary approach to open science. It is our hope that the catalogue, as it continues to evolve, will play a significant role in propelling environmental research towards new horizons of discovery and innovation.

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8 Annex A - Glossary

AAAI:	Authentication, Authorisation, and Accounting Infrastructure
CERIF:	Common European Research Information Format
DCAT:	Data Catalogue Vocabulary
EPOS-DCAT-AP:	DCAT Application Profile for EPOS
DDSS:	Data, Data products, Software and Services
DIAS:	Data and Information Access Services
EOSC:	European Open Science Cloud
EPOS Strategic Plan:	Defines the activities of EPOS-ERIC
GEP:	Geohazards Exploitation Platform
ICS-C:	Integrated Core Services - Central Hub
ICS-D:	Distributed Integrated Core Services Distributed
PID:	Persistent Identifier
SDLC:	Software Development Life Cycle
TCS:	Thematic Core Services